

LLM-Assisted Metadata Extraction and Normalization for Historical Correspondence: A Multi-Stage Pipeline Approach

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The structured extraction of metadata from historical correspondence is a key component of letter edition projects. Although encoding standards such as the Correspondence Metadata Interchange Format (CMIF) and infrastructures like *correspSearch* (Dumont et al. 2025) are available, metadata generation workflows largely rely on manual annotation or rule-based systems (Alyafeai et al. 2025). These approaches are often limited in handling orthographic variability, archaic date formats, multilingualism, and contextual ambiguity that characterize historical correspondence (Li, 2018; McGillivray et al. 2020).

Recent studies indicate that Large Language Models (LLMs) can effectively support labor-intensive tasks in digital edition projects that require context-sensitive semantic interpretation (Czmiel et al. 2024; Pollin, 2024; Scholger, Strutz, & Pollin 2024). To contribute to the ongoing discourse on the feasibility, potential benefits, and limitations of LLM-assisted processes, systematic testing and evaluation of these technologies within DH scenarios is essential.

This paper presents a comprehensive multi-stage pipeline approach that leverages LLMs for metadata extraction and normalization while addressing the specific requirements of historical correspondence digitization, placing text-centered approaches within a broader methodological context. Through systematic evaluation using the Joseph von Hammer-Purgstall correspondence collection, we examine both

the capabilities and limitations of current LLM technology for this task.

Material and Dataset

The Joseph von Hammer-Purgstall correspondence (1774–1856) encompasses over 3,500 letters from a print edition that were transformed into a digital edition reflecting current DH standards (Stadler, Illetschko, and Seifert 2016). It is well-suited for the given problem through its multilingual content (German, French, Italian, English), the wide geographical range, and historical complexity, including orthographic variations in place names, inconsistent personal name spellings and abbreviated names, as well as variable date formats.

The material comprises transcribed letters and editorial and partially normalized correspondence metadata (writer, recipient, date and place of letter) from the published print editions (Höflehner et al. 2021) that have been linked to GND and GeoNames recently, serving as ground truth. For purposes of fair evaluation, we distinguish between metadata that can be extracted from letter transcriptions alone and information that requires access to external archival materials, biographical databases, correspondent networks, or institutional knowledge not present in the transcribed texts themselves. The metadata material will therefore need to be reviewed and revised to reflect this scope accordingly.

To empirically validate our approach, a curated sample of 100 letters will be selected. This stratified sample will reflect the collection's inherent challenges, including letters lacking sender or recipient information, abbreviated personal or geographical references, implicit addressees, and non-standardized date expressions. This stratification ensures comprehensive evaluation across varying levels of metadata completeness.

Methodology

We use a multi-stage pipeline that transforms raw textual data into interoperable CMIF-compliant metadata. Rather than relying exclusively on LLMs, our approach minimizes their use to subtasks requiring semantic understanding, while leveraging established pre-processing scripts for other components. The pipeline implementation prioritizes computational efficiency and scholarly transparency. Each processing stage generates comprehensive logging and intermediate outputs, enabling researchers to trace decision-making processes and validate results. The modular architecture allows for selective reprocessing of individual stages when ground truth annotations are refined or when improved LLM models become available. API rate limiting and error handling ensure robust batch processing capabilities suitable for large correspondence collections, while maintaining respectful usage of external authority services.

Stage 1: LLM-Based Metadata Extraction

The initial stage employs LLMs to analyze correspondence transcriptions and extract core metadata elements: sender, recipient, date, and place of writing. In the context of historical text sources, this process traditionally involves significant manual effort to resolve ambiguities introduced by variant spellings of person and place names, multilingual content, archaic date formats, and ambiguous references that require contextual understanding for proper identification and disambiguation. Context-sensitive LLMs are assumed to be better equipped to handle these challenges than rule-based approaches. Using a simple prompt design, the extraction process generates structured JSON output with confidence scores, reflecting the model's internal certainty about extraction accuracy—a mechanism to flag items with lower scores for manual review allowing efficient allocation of scholarly attention to ambiguous cases rather than providing absolute quality guarantees. This stage focuses on normalizing extracted entities into consistent forms suitable for subsequent authority linking while preserving variant information for scholarly reference.

Stage 2: Authority Linking via APIs

The creation of interoperable correspondence metadata, particularly in formats compatible with the CMIF standard, requires not only accurate entity extraction but also successful linking to authoritative databases such as the Gemeinsame Normdatei (GND) and GeoNames. Extracted and normalized entities are systematically linked to authoritative databases through dedicated APIs. We separate LLM processing from authority linking to ensure reliability and avoid the hallucination risks associated with direct LLM-generated URIs.

Stage 3: Contextual Disambiguation

When multiple authority matches exist, an LLM-based disambiguation process analyzes the full letter content and selects the most appropriate match according to the historical context. This addresses a critical limitation of simple heuristic approaches (such as selecting locations by population size) that may be inappropriate for historical contexts. For example, when disambiguating "Vienna," the system considers the historical period, correspondent backgrounds, and letter content to distinguish between Vienna, Austria and Vienna, Virginia. The LLM evaluation incorporates historical relevance, geographical context, professional networks, and cultural factors specific to the correspondence period. When automated disambiguation confidence scores fall below established thresholds, the system flags entries for manual expert review, maintaining scholarly accuracy while maximizing computational efficiency.

Stage 4: CMIF Generation

The final stage converts disambiguated metadata into CMIF, creating interoperable correspondence descriptions suitable for integration with correspSearch and other DH platforms. This includes the proper generation of the <correspDesc> element, following TEI Guidelines for correspondence markup, and authoritative URI integration. The generated CMIF metadata enables sophisticated network analysis and visualization approaches that transform individual correspondence study into systematic investigation of

communication patterns, geographical networks, and temporal dynamics.

With this final stage, the Hammer-Purgstall correspondence is transformed from a collection of individual letters into a comprehensive dataset for studying 19th-century scholarly networks, diplomatic communication patterns, and cross-cultural intellectual exchange.

The multi-stage structure reflects a design principle prioritizing interpretability and modularity, allowing individual components to be independently tested, replaced, or refined. This modularity also facilitates reuse through adaptation to varying editorial practices and project-specific constraints. The pipeline architecture further incorporates fallback mechanisms for handling processing failures, ensuring robust operation across diverse correspondence collections.

Preliminary Observations

A critical methodological consideration involves establishing appropriate ground truth standards for evaluation. Our approach uses existing editorial metadata from the published print editions as ground truth but restricts evaluation to metadata genuinely inferable from transcriptions alone to create fair evaluation conditions for LLM performance assessment.

Initial pipeline implementation suggests that basic entity extraction may be feasible using LLM-based approaches, though comprehensive evaluation remains to be conducted. We hypothesize that contextual disambiguation could potentially outperform simple population-based heuristics for geographical entity resolution, as LLMs may be able to leverage historical context that simpler algorithms cannot access.

Based on our preliminary analysis of the corpus characteristics, we anticipate several categories of extraction challenges that will require systematic investigation: highly abbreviated references may prove difficult to resolve without extensive context; implicit addressees, which appear common in formal correspondence of this period, may present identification challenges; and dates expressed through religious or cultural references rather than standard calendar notation may require specialized handling approaches.

These preliminary observations will guide our systematic evaluation methodology, but definitive conclusions about system performance and error patterns must await comprehensive testing against our established ground truth dataset.

Evaluation Approach and Metrics

Given the complexity of the task, we employ stage-specific evaluation strategies to identify performance bottlenecks and guide system refinement. For Stage 1 (entity extraction), possible metrics include precision, recall, and F1 scores, with particular attention to variant spellings and multilingual data. Stage 2 (authority linking) may be assessed

sed in terms of match success rates and the quality of candidate selection processes. Evaluating the Stage 3 disambiguation component will likely require expert judgment to compare LLM-generated contextual decisions against human interpretations. Beyond accuracy, we also aim to consider the interpretability and transparency of LLM reasoning, especially in terms of its potential scholarly value. Finally, systematic error analysis will be necessary to categorize failure types and inform targeted system adjustments.

Cross-model comparison will examine performance differences between proprietary models (e.g., GPT-4, Claude Sonnet) and open-source alternatives (e.g., Qwen3, OLMo2), addressing broader concerns regarding sustainability and reproducibility in DH infrastructures. While proprietary models currently demonstrate superior performance in many tasks, the potential for service discontinuation or access restrictions necessitates parallel development using open alternatives. Our evaluation framework thus contributes to community discussions about model selection strategies that balance performance requirements with long-term accessibility and reproducibility standards essential for scholarly research.

Contributions

This research contributes methodologically to digital humanities by demonstrating scalable approaches to correspondence metadata extraction that maintain scholarly standards while reducing manual annotation requirements. The multi-stage architecture provides modularity allowing adaptation to different correspondence collections and languages, while the authority linking integration ensures interoperability with existing DH infrastructure.

The contextual disambiguation innovation addresses a genuine limitation in current automated approaches, offering potential applications beyond correspondence to other entity-rich historical documents. The systematic evaluation framework provides benchmarking capabilities for future research in LLM-assisted historical document processing.

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